

Research paper

Formal and non formal education in school children's

Jayanthi C

¹Department of Education, Annamalai University, Tamilnadu, India.

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Accordingly, the syllabus in all the subjects in Tamil Nadu, the sex education syllabus followed in the two Indian states, Kerala and Maharashtra, and in two western countries of Sweden and U.S.A., the literature in general on sex education, and the report of UNESCO institute for Education, was subjected to a close study. In the light of this knowledge, a draft syllabus for sex education was prepared and in order that opinion on the content of the syllabus might be obtained, the respondents were requested to tick off those items they would like to recommend for inclusion in a programme of sex education at the higher secondary school students in Tamilnadu.

Key words: Education, formal education, Informal education Information.

Introduction

Education may be formal or informal. Information given in any institution with definite objectives and render a systematic plan is formation education. In the Indian set up, formal education is imported mainly by educational institutions an informal education by the family and other agencies such as TV, radio, cinema, internet etc. Sex education is not offered systematically in any institution in the state. Each individual acquires his sex information from informal agencies. Information education is generally unsystematic and irregular and the places of information that are acquired particularly on matters like sex cannot be organized complete or correct, so much so that the influence of such as education is likely to be harmful to mental health. At this point, it has to be emphasized that the extent of the harmful effect depends upon the nature of the agencies of informal education therefore; any attempt to give formal sex education should be proceeded by the identification of the different sources of sex information for student. Therefore the investigator has enquired into their problem.

The identification referred to above can be attempted in two ways, one b directly asking the students themselves, and the other, by asking those concerned with the education of our youngsters, to mention the sources of sex information for students. The students under this study put the following questions. For more than one reason people do not agree in their views regarding the idea of introducing sex education in the curriculum, the educational level of which it is to be introduced, etc. Some people feel that sex education should be imported not by teaches but by parents.

This is opposed by others who believe that in India where two-thirds of the populations are illiterate, it is not possible for the parents to impart sex education to their children. A few others feel that schools should supplement sex education imported by the parents. In order to study (a) the prevailing opinion on the idea of introducing sex education in the higher secondary school education in the higher secondary school students (b) the reasons against the idea and (c) the aims and values of imparting sex education.

The people who recognize the importance of sex education at the higher secondary school level, however on the questions of the place of sex education in the curriculum and the content of the syllabus for sex education. To secure the opinion of the respondents about the place of sex education. One of the aspects of sex education to be investigated in a study of this kind pertains to the construction of a suitable syllabus. The chief principle in curriculum construction is that no evolving curriculum should be considered in isolation. In other words, any new curriculum should be continuity with the curriculum existing in the country and those in other countries. Therefore, there should be no gap between the new curriculum in sex education and the curriculum in other subjects on the one hand and between this curriculum and the one followed in other countries and in some status in India, on the other.

Instructions in sex education need some special training to do the job, because formal sex education is a new subject in the Indian educational is a new subject in the Indian education system. This aspect had to be considered keeping in mind that it did not concern the students directly. Comprehensive sex Education is effective and does not

promote sexual risks,” (Checkoway B 2012). As said according to the website Youth for Advocates. Sex Education is currently taught in elementary school, only in physical education and it is taught in Middle School, but only one semester and the same for high school in the United States of America.

A number of commission reports, seminars and conferences have stressed need for attitude of sex education in Indian schools, but response towards it on the part of schools and curriculum has been neither active nor enthusiastic. Any delay in implementing the attitude of sex education, could have undesirable effects on the character of the growing young generation. The education is the curriculum developers feel that it is the need for hour that our pupils should be given every opportunity to develop attitude of sex education.

Materials and methods

The sex education attitude scale used for the pilot study is given in Appendix – A. the Tamil version of the scale is given in Appendix-B.

Dimensions of the sex education attitude scale final

Sex education attitude scale consists of four dimensions namely,

- a) General factors
- b) Social factors
- c) Individual mental factors
- d) Individual physical factors

The sex education attitude scale has 40 items, the general factors has 10 items, the social factors has 10 items, the individual mental factors 10 items, the individual physical factors 10 items.

Reliability of the scale

Test retest methods were followed for testing the reliability of the present scale. For estimating the test retest reliability of the scale, the scale was administered twice on a sample of 100 higher secondary school students and the co-efficient of reliability was found to be 0.83.

Validity of the scale

The validity of the present scale was examined with the help of content validity. This was done by examining how well the contents of the scale represented the subject matter under study. The statements were given to 20 experts in the field to judge the content validity. Further the validity value was found to be 0.92 by taking the square-root of reliability co-efficient.

Adolescent's Emotional Adjustment Inventory

It is true man is a social being surrounded by numerous problems which are proclaimed daily, in living colour and in a best-selling literature of turmoil, alienations and despair challenging his adjustment. The problem of adjustment “have been bemoaned and deplored by every generation since long before the Christian Era (Karl Meninger).

The history of adjustment actually begins with early man's awareness of the extremely deviant and disturbed individual. The concept of adjustment originated in biology and has been derived from Darwin's concept of Evolutions in the mid eighteenth century which was later on, borrowed by the psychologist and renewed as ‘adjustment’ which refers to ‘an index of integration between needs and satisfaction and is related to achievement, social acceptance, age, sex, economic security and moral standards Chauhan, Tiwari and Khattar, (1973). An individual's adjustment largely depends on his action and interaction in the course of his competence in meeting his biological and psycho-social needs within the frame work of environmental facilities and constraints. The individual adjust both socially as well as emotionally for a successful and happy life. Emotional adjustment is a prerequisite for social adjustment, as found that emotionally well-adjusted persons are quick to establish, affectional relations with others, Both ‘emotion’ and ‘motivation’ come from the same Latin word meaning ‘motion’ or ‘to move’ emotions are stirred up moments’ or ‘stirred up Falling’s our emotional adjustment are related to those feelings which are usually correlated with activity in the automatic nervous system. Emotions stress the body by using up its resources at a faster than usual rate. In nut shell, we can say on emotionally well-adjusted individual, particularly the adolescents, is not only coefficient and happy with his environment but also he must have a sense of social and emotional feelings. As such items, which help to assess the above mentioned aspects of emotional adjustment, are included in the present inventory, mainly for discriminating well emotionally adjusted adolescents from the poorly emotionally adjusted adolescents. In the present investigation, the investigator used adolescent emotional adjustment inventory by Patil,(1989). Which is a useful device to assess emotional adjustment of higher secondary students and college going. Age range (16 to 20 years).

As per the tool constructor, the items were selected, after careful examinations from available standard inventories, and where necessary, were slightly modified, some new items were also included in the light of the description of the variables. In the preliminary form, there were 80 items. After the pilot study, only 60 items were retained. For the pilot study, the inventory was pretested on 197 subjects age range (6 to 25 years). In order to select the items, it was decided to find out validity indices of the items following the procedure given by Garret, H.E. The total scores on each of the item of the preliminary sample (N-197) were arranged in the decreasing order and 27 percent of the top and 27 percent of the bottom scores were identified. These groups are to be called technically high and low groups. The number of persons in the high and the low groups.

There are thirty five statements followed by 'yes', 'no' responses. Kindly go through them carefully. If you agree with the statement then tick (✓) mark before the column of 'yes' and if don't agree then tick (✓) mark before 'no' respond to all the statements without leaving any.

Reliability and validity

The reliability of the tool was well established by the tool constructor which was found to be 0.87. The full possess content validity and face validity as per the tool constructor. However, the present investigator translated the tool in to tamil and adopted test-retest method by giving the tool to 100 higher secondary students twice after a gap of 15 days. And the reliability was found to be 0.86.

Scoring

The scoring system of the inventory is very simple. As mentioned earlier, each item has two response (ie) yes or no. for the subjects response of yes, score of 2 should be given and incase of no response 1 score.

Social Adjustment Inventory

The social adjustment inventory consists of 60 statements. The statement to know the social adjustment of the students on the social adjustment aspects. The tools was constructed and standardized by Roma Pal, (1985). The reliability of the tool was 82. The investigator also found the reliability of the translated Tamil version of the tool and it was found to be 0.8314 using test-retest methods. The social adjustment inventory was used for the present study.

Attitude towards sex education tool

There are forty statements in the tool. The maximum score for an individual is 200 and a minimum is 40. Those

Mean and standard deviation of attitude towards introduction of sex education scores- Dimension IV individual mental factor

It may be recalled that the attitude towards the introduction of sex education in relation to certain selected sub-samples were analysed Dimension wice the analyses of dimension IV individual mental factor is calculated and the results are discussed.

Dimension - IV Individual mental factor

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation attitude towards introduction of sex education scores - Dimension IV- individual mental factor
Table No. 4.6

S.No	Categories	N	M Maxi:50	SD	Level	
Entire – sample		600	37.97	6.49	HF	
1.	Gender	Male	274	38.06	7.16	HF
		Female	326	37.89	5.88	HF
2.	Religion	Hindu	455	37.30	6.53	HF
		Christian	60	37.65	5.44	HF
		Muslim	85	41.79	5.64	HF
3	Type of management	Government	363	37.04	6.73	HF
		Aided	217	39.87	5.69	HF
		Private	20	34.15	5.21	HF
4	Locality	Urban	142	40.73	6.31	HF
		Rural	458	37.11	6.31	HF
5	Type of school	Co education	476	37.41	6.25	HF

candidate whose scores are between 40 to 65 are having favourable attitude towards sex education in schools, where as those scores ranging between 66 to 135 are categorized as medium level of favourable attitude towards sex education and those candidates whose scores are ranging from 136 to 200 are having highly favourable attitude towards sex education.

Similarly for factor wise also the same categorisation was followed. Those scores are ranging from 10 to 16 are unfavourable category, those scores are ranging from 17 to 34 are medium level of favourable attitude and those scores ranging from 35 to 50 are having highly favourable attitude towards sex education. Accordingly, the scores of an individual ranges from 0 to 66. Those scores are between 0 to 22 are having low level of emotional adjustment: those scores are ranging from 23 to 42 are having average level of emotional adjustment and those scores are ranging from 43 to 66 are having high level of adolescent emotional adjustment.

In the case of social adjustment scale, the tool constructor has given the categorisation. Accordingly, the scores of an individual ranges from 0 to 120. Those scores are between 0 to 40 are having low level of emotional adjustment: those scores are ranging from 41 to 80 are having average level of social adjustment and those scores are ranging from 81 to 120 are having high level of social adjustment.

Results and discussion

After the analysis of data the result are presented with interpretations and graphical representation also. The data collected from 600 higher secondary students in Cuddalore educational district who were taken as sample. The data were analyzed using the following statistical methods.

6	Parental education	Boys	101	40.18	7.29	HF
		Girls	23	39.74	5.50	HF
		Illiterate	183	37.64	5.94	HF
		School level	367	38.25	6.47	HF
		Graduate	40	36.95	8.92	HF
		Professional	10	37.7	6.06	HF
7	Family type	Joint	183	38.34	7.35	HF
		Nuclear	417	37.80	6.08	HF

HF- Highly Favourable

It may be inferred that the mean of Dimension - IV (individual mental factor) of attitude towards introduction of sex education of higher secondary students is ($M = 37.97$). This indicates that there is a favorable attitude towards introduction of the individual mental factor among higher secondary students. Although all the sub-samples are having favourable attitude towards introduction of sex education of general factor there are slight differences among the variables. Female students, students of muslim religion, government school students, rural students, girls school students, students of professional parents and students of joint family are having more favourable attitude towards introduction of the sex education general factor than their

respective counterparts. The standard deviation scores of all the factors show greater consistency among themselves.

Mean Standard deviation of Adolescent emotional adjustment scores of - entire and sub-samples.

One of the objectives of the present study is to find out the higher secondary students adolescent emotional adjustment. For this purpose the adolescent emotional adjustment inventory constructed by Patil (1989) has been used by the investigator. The mean and standard deviation were calculated for the entire sample and its sub samples too. The results were given in the following

Table 2. Mean and Standard deviation of Adolescent emotional adjustment scores of higher secondary students

S.No	Categories	N	M	SD	Level	
	Entire - sample	600	48.89	5.86	High	
1.	Gender	Male	274	49.56	5.25	High
		Female	326	48.32	6.29	High
2.	Religion	Hindu	455	48.46	6.10	High
		Christian	60	48.92	5.32	High
		Muslim	85	51.13	4.27	High
3	Type of management	Government	363	48.52	5.74	High
		Aided	217	49.56	5.98	High
		Private	20	48.20	6.46	High
4	Locality	Urban	142	48.93	5.41	High
		Rural	458	48.87	5.99	High
5	Type of school	Co education	476	48.29	5.99	High
		Boys	101	51.00	4.10	High
		Girls	23	51.91	6.89	High
6	Parents education	Illiterate	183	48.70	6.11	High
		School level	367	48.72	5.81	High
		Graduate	40	51.10	5.35	High
		Professional	10	49.20	3.68	High

7	Family type	Joint	183	49.94	5.61	High
		Nuclear	417	48.42	5.92	High

H- High level of adolescent emotional adjustment

The mean and standard deviation of the entire sample is found to be $M = 48.89$ and $S.D. = 5.86$, respectively. It may be recalled that those scores ranging from 43 to 66 are having high level of adolescent emotional adjustment. It is concluded that the higher secondary students have high level of adolescent emotional adjustment. Although all the sub-samples are having high level of adolescent emotional adjustment, there are slight differences in the levels.

Among the gender of the higher secondary students, male students have higher level of adolescent emotional adjustment ($M = 49.56$) than female higher secondary students ($M = 48.32$). Among the students of various religion, muslim higher secondary students secured the highest ($M = 51.13$) place in adolescent emotional adjustment followed by christian ($M = 48.92$) higher secondary students and hindu ($M = 48.46$) higher secondary students.

Considering the nature of the management, the higher secondary students studying in aided ($M = 49.56$) School possess the highest level of adolescent emotional adjustment ($M=49.56$) followed by government ($M = 48.52$) and private ($M = 48.20$) school students. Urban higher secondary students ($M=48.93$) registered higher adolescent emotional adjustment than rural ($M=48.87$) higher secondary students. Considering the type of school the higher secondary students

studying in Girls school ($M = 51.91$) possess highest level of adolescent emotional adjustment followed by boys ($M = 51.00$) and co education ($M = 48.29$) higher secondary students.

This higher secondary students whose parents are graduate are having highest level adolescent emotional adjustment, ($M=51.10$) followed by students of professional parents ($M = 49.20$) school level educated parents ($M = 48.72$) and illiterate (48.70) parents. Joint family higher secondary students ($M=49.94$) registered higher adolescent emotional adjustment than nuclear family ($M=48.42$) higher secondary students.

Mean and Standard deviation of social adjustment scores of entire and sub-samples

It may be recalled that one of the objective of this study is to find out the higher secondary students social adjustment. For this purpose the social adjustment inventory constructed has been administered by the investigator. The data were collected from them. The mean and standard deviation were calculated for the entire sample and its sub samples.

Table 3 Mean and Standard deviation of social adjustment scores of higher secondary students

S.No	Categories	N	M maxi:120	SD	Level	
	Entire - sample	600	93.94	7.74	High	
1.	Gender	Male	274	93.60	7.84	High
		Female	326	94.23	7.65	High
2.	Religion	Hindu	455	94.07	7.95	High
		Christian	60	93.43	8.02	High
		Muslim	85	93.61	6.28	High
3	Type of management	Government	363	94.53	7.49	High
		Aided	217	93.18	8.11	High
		Private	20	91.55	7.01	High
4	Locality	Urban	142	93.94	7.80	High
		Rural	458	93.94	7.73	High
5	Type of school	Co education	476	94.16	7.92	High

		Boys	101	93.41	6.79	High
		Girls	23	91.70	7.53	High
6	Parental education	Illiterate	183	93.27	8.25	High
		School level	367	94.60	7.40	High
		Graduate	40	90.83	7.89	High
		Professional	10	94.70	6.40	High
		Joint	183	93.30	7.14	High
7	Family type	Joint	183	93.30	7.14	High
		Nuclear	417	94.23	7.97	High

H- High level of social adjustment

It may be inferred that the mean of the social adjustment of the entire sample is 93.94. It indicates the high level of social adjustment of the higher secondary students. Since the scores are between 81 to 120 categories which is categorized as high level of emotional adjustment. The higher secondary students whose parents are professional (M=94.70) are having highest level of social adjustment (M=94.70) followed by students of school level parents (M=94.60) illiterate level parents (M=93.27) and graduate (M=90.83) parents. Nuclear family higher secondary students (M = 94.23) registered higher social adjustments than Joint family (M=93.30) higher secondary students.

Differential analysis involves the most important procedure by which the researcher is able to make inferences involving the determination of the statistical significance of difference between groups with reference to selected variables. It involves the use of 't' test. A 't' test is a numerical procedure that takes into account the difference between means of two groups, the number of subjects, in each groups and the amount of variation of spread present in the scores. Thus, the 't' test is used to determine whether the performance of two group is significant or not. In order to know the statistical significance of the difference between the two groups, the researcher calculated the 't' test and 'F' test if more than two sub- samples are involved. The same analysis was done for all the three research variables wise attitude towards introduction of sex education, factor wise, adolescent emotional adjustment and social adjustment. The result are discussed in the following pages.

Conclusion

After finalizing the selection of all tools, the data were collected from 600 higher secondary students comprising

various sub-samples as the mentioned earlier in the chapter. Than the data were subjected to statistical analysis.

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